

Sustainable energy generation: Assessing the potential of sewage sludge and polyethylene-based fuel for energy applications

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ABSTRACT

This study explored the potential of using sewage sludge (SS) and polyethylene (PE) waste as alternative fuels within a circular economy framework. SS, characterized by a high-water content and the presence of heavy metals, and PE, a byproduct of the automotive industry with a high calorific value, were pelletized and co-incinerated in a fluidized bed combustor. The primary objective of this study was to assess the energy recovery potential and environmental impact of these materials individually and in a 1:1 blend. Life cycle assessment (LCA) methodology was employed to evaluate the environmental footprint, focusing on pollutant emissions and energy consumption during incineration. The results indicated that the co-incineration of SS and PE significantly increased the low heating value of the fuel, enhancing its competitiveness as an energy source. However, this process also led to a notable increase in pollutant emissions, particularly NO_x and SO₂. Despite these challenges, this study demonstrates the feasibility of developing a sustainable alternative fuel from SS and PE, contributing to waste reduction and energy recovery in line with circular economic principles.

1. Introduction

An essential approach in the context of a circular economy is the use of waste materials, such as sewage sludge (SS) and automotive residual products in the form of polymers, most commonly polyethylene (PE) (Mannina and Mineo, 2023). Moreover, the energy potential of SS from wastewater treatment plants is limitless (Lou et al., 2023), with 9.5 million tons of dry SS produced in the European Union in 2017 (Jadlovec et al., 2023). SS is characterized by high content of water (>80 %), microorganisms, nitrogen and phosphorus, and heavy metals in the form of iron, cobalt, mercury, etc. (Chen et al., 2020). The average low heating value (LHV) of dry SS is 12 – 16 MJ•kg⁻¹ (Wzorek, 2012). Furthermore, the automotive industry produces waste materials, such as PE and other plastics (Spalding and Chatterjee, 2017). An average car weighing 1300 kg contains 12 – 15 % plastic, corresponding to approximately 150 – 200 kg (Merkisz-Guranowska, 2018). The LHV of plastic residues can reach up to 40 MJ•kg⁻¹ (Zhou et al., 2014). Based on the EU2000/53/EC directive, which specifies recovery and recycling rates of 95 % and 85 %, respectively, for end-of-life vehicles, (Smolnik, 2014) the aim is to recycle as much material as possible. However, residual products that cannot be reprocessed have great

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potential for energy recovery (Yang et al., 2021).

The energy recovery potential of waste materials, such as SS and PE, is possible through two methods: anaerobic digestion (Duan et al., 2012) and thermal processes, such as pyrolysis (Anuar Sharuddin et al., 2016), gasification, (Werle and Sobek, 2019) or incineration (Liang et al., 2021a). These methods can convert waste into thermal or electrical energy, which can contribute to energy sustainability and waste reduction in society.

Study by (Siyal et al., 2023) assessed pellet production intensity based on sewage sludge, and their results showed that temperature, pressure, and type of material have a significant impact on pellet parameters. Specifically, SS pellets were characterized by low volumetric energy density ($12.97 \text{ kJ}\cdot\text{cm}^{-3}$) and low *LHV* ($8.04 \pm 0.02 \text{ MJ}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}$). An objective of this study was to blend dried SS with PE, which would result in a significant increase in *LHV* and thus, a greater competitive ability of this alternative fuel. Plastics in pellets also contribute to an increase in calorific value, because the monomer structures in plastics are characterized by the ability to store large amounts of energy (Wei et al., 2024). Plastics can be used as binders during pelletization. For example, when co-pelletizing plastics with biomass, the plastics behave as binders, creating a strong mechanical connection between the products (Emadi et al., 2017). These bonds are attributed to their low softening temperature ($110 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$) and melting temperature ($170 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$) (Peng et al., 2021).

Research from (Lundin et al., 2004) conducted environmental and economic evaluations of various SS management methods. Their findings indicated that the co-incineration of sewage sludge is the most effective approach for energy recovery, although it may incur higher costs and contribute to increased pollutant emissions. Study by (Yao et al., 2022) described the thermal degradation of plastic waste such as PE. Their study reported that 750,000 t of waste is burned per day worldwide, and the degree of heat recovery depends on the calorific value and type of waste. However, incineration of this waste can generate toxic gases such as dioxins ($\text{C}_4\text{H}_4\text{O}_2$), carbon monoxide (CO), and hydrogen sulfide (H_2S), which can have a serious impact on human health (Verma et al., 2016).

Study by (Naveen et al., 2023) described solar technology represents a promising alternative to conventional fossil energy sources. This review explores the integration of solar energy into biomass conversion processes, aiming to enable fully renewable production of biofuels and high-value bioproducts.

Recent studies from (Priyadharsini et al., 2023) have explored thermochemical processes such as biomass pyrolysis not only for waste management but also for the production of functional materials like biochar. Similarly, the conversion of waste streams into valuable energy carriers such as hydrogen highlights the growing potential of alternative fuels in sustainable energy systems.

Currently, sustainable energy production is a key topic in environmental research and industrial innovation (Li and Ge, 2023). Therefore, this study aimed to analyze the environmental footprints of two alternative energy sources: sludge and PE-based fuels, similar as (Gao et al., 2021). The pellet-based fuel production intensity was assessed using raw materials from SS and PE, which were employed in a fluidized bed combustor for co-incineration, where he described the concept of combustion in a fluidized bed combustor (Lasek et al., 2021). Prior to incineration, both original materials were converted into pellets, and their compositions were analyzed using ultimate and proximate analyses, with additional assessments of ash content and moisture content. Further, the flue gas composition, potential for energy recovery from SS and its subsequent environmental implications were evaluated. An incineration method for SS was explored, both in its pure form and when mixed with PE, with an emphasis on promoting a circular economy through SS and PE recovery. An analytical LCA method was used for the gate-to-gate (Chelvam et al., 2023) incineration process of selected waste-derived fuels to investigate the differences and possible benefits of their co-incineration. Notably, this study exclusively considered pollutant production values within the LCA, and the primary focus was on energy consumption for fuel production. SS was studied from an energy recovery perspective by (Ding et al., 2021). This study reviews the environmental challenges of coal gangue, including heavy metal leaching and harmful gas emissions. It highlights its impacts on soil, water, and air quality. Solutions like using coal gangue in construction and land reclamation are discussed to reduce its environmental impact. The energy recovery from plastic waste was investigated by (Vlasopoulos et al., 2023). This study followed trends in the scientific field and provides new insights into the context of existing scientific publications that focus on the LCA of different types of waste-derived fuels. Further, it contributes to and supports the pillars of a circular economy by enhancing waste management practices.

The specific objectives of this work are: (i) to develop and characterize a novel alternative fuel by blending SS and PE waste in a 1:1 ratio, with an emphasis on improving fuel properties such as *LHV*, hardness, and water resistance; (ii) to experimentally evaluate the co-incineration process of SS and PE pellets in a fluidized bed combustor, focusing on combustion behavior, pollutant emissions, and energy recovery efficiency; (iii) to conduct a gate-to-gate LCA of the incineration process to quantify and compare the environmental impacts of pure SS, pure PE, and the blended fuel; and (iv) to assess the feasibility of using SS-PE blends as sustainable alternative fuels within the framework of a circular economy, considering both their environmental footprint and practical applicability in energy systems.

This article was motivated by the search for alternatives to conventional fossil fuels. The Czech Republic has significant reserves of sewage sludge requiring energy recovery to avoid landfilling. Additionally, a partner provided access to polyethylene waste from the automotive industry, which, due to its high *LHV*, shows potential as an additive to other fuels. This study presents great potential in terms of developing an alternative fuel that will simultaneously reduce the amount of SS and PE waste and be competitive in terms of a *LHV* ($9.83 - 31.81 \text{ MJ}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}$) and structure. The novelty lies in the use of two unconventional materials and the original approach towards their use, assessing their qualities in terms of their properties and environmental impact.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Sewage sludge processing

Prior to incineration, SS underwent a series of treatments, including dewatering, drying, and pelletizing. Originating from a sewage

treatment facility in the Czech Republic, the raw materials initially contained a moisture content of 95 wt%, which was reduced to 84 wt% through mechanical dewatering. Subsequent drying in a paddle batch dryer at 180 °C for 60 min further reduced the moisture content to 21.8 wt% (Ricciardi et al., 2020). To preserve consistent fuel properties, particularly moisture content, the processed fuel was stored under controlled conditions in the fuel preparation laboratory, maintaining constant ambient temperature 25 °C and relative humidity levels of 40 % in airtight containers. Given the risk of elevated water vapor content in the flue gas due to high fuel moisture, precautions were taken to prevent condensation on the chamber walls to ensure accurate experimental results. The entire chamber is equipped with an external heat source and sufficient insulation to prevent dew point underrun. The dewatering and drying stages were succeeded by pelletization using an MGB 100 – BONSAI (KOVO NOVAK, Czech Republic) pelletizer, capable of processing up to 300 kg•h⁻¹ with a power input of 6 kW and yielding pellets of 25 mm in length and 5 mm in diameter.

2.2. Automotive waste production

The input material was a synthetic material consisting of a base component, PE polymer (99 %), with the addition of materials such as polypropylene, polyvinyl chloride, and polyurethane. The material was obtained from a company in the Czech Republic, which is engaged in the production of components containing the material mentioned above. The maximum input moisture content of the material was 0.89 wt%, and the particle size was up to 3 cm. A pellet press (STILER, Poland) with a power of 7.5 kW was used for pelletization.

2.3. Blended alternative fuel development

A single blended mixture, which contained 50 % sewage sludge and 50 % automotive waste (SS 1:1 PE), was obtained, and the individual components were measured by volume. The densities of PE and SS were 141 kg•m⁻³ and 1200 kg•m⁻³, respectively. The mixtures were homogenized using an ALBA mixer (ALBA, Czech Republic). The moisture contents of the mixtures and produced pellets were measured using a Mettler-Toledo device (Mettler-Toledo, Switzerland).

2.4. Analyses

The angle of repose (AOR) was assessed for SS and PE. A vibrating conveyor facilitated the movement of the material, allowing it to form a conical shape upon settling in a designated area. The shape was photographed from eight perspectives and analyzed using the eScope program. The flowability according to the angle of repose was determined based on the flow characterization (Simek et al., 2017). The particle size distribution was determined solely for SS owing to the large particle size of PE, rendering it unsuitable for sieve analysis. Instead, a scaled photocomparison method was employed. The sieve analysis used Fritsch (Germany) sieves with mesh sizes of 1 000, 1 400, 2 000, 2 500, 3 150, 5 000, 6 300, 8 000, and 10 000 µm. Pelletization was conducted using a STILER pellet press with a 7.5 kW power output. The material was extruded through the die perimeter holes using a rolling mechanism. Pelletization occurred at a die temperature of 70 °C, monitored by an embedded temperature sensor, and the resulting pellets had diameters of 6 cm. The Wettability Index (W) was used to gauge water absorption resistance, with pellets immersed in 27 °C water for 1 min. Hardness was quantified using a pellet hardness tester (Amandus Kahl, Germany), a motor-driven device that facilitates easy measurement, with the results presented in kilograms.

Ultimate and proximate analyses (UPA) were conducted to assess the fuel according to standards (ISO 29541:2010, ISO 19579:2006, ISO 687:2010, and ISO 1171:2010). The mass concentrations of various elements in raw state (x^r) (C^r , H^r , N^r , S^r , O^r , W^r , and A^r in water and ash) were measured using CHNS628 and CHNS628S analyzers (Leco, USA) based on the thermogravimetric (Dumas) principle. O₂ levels were determined gravimetrically as the difference after heating the sample above the boiling point of water using a VF110 electric furnace (Mettler, Germany), per ISO 181234-2. The A^r content was analyzed in an LEO 5/11 furnace (LAC, Czech Republic) according to ISO 18122. LHV was assessed according to ISO 18125.

The flue gas was subjected to Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) using an AtmosFIRt gas analyzer (Protea, UK) to evaluate CO, CO₂, NO, NO₂, N₂O, NH₃, HCl, SO₂, CH₄, HF, and O₂ contents (Laudal et al., 2003; Wang et al., 2011). Mercury was analyzed using an HM-1400 TRX mercury analyzer (Durag, Germany) to monitor Hg^t, which represents the sum of Hg⁰ and Hg²⁺ (Čespiva et al., 2022). Further details on the functionality of the analyzer are provided in the study by (Górecki et al., 2016). The ultimate and proximate analyses properties of PE, SS, and the blend are listed in Table A.1.

2.5. Experimental fluidized-bed incineration setup

The experiments were conducted in a fluidized-bed combustor, see Figure A.2. This pilot-scale unit utilizes a screw conveyor to introduce fuel into the combustor, capable of processing up to 4.5 kg•h⁻¹. An electric resistance heater with a 7 kW power input was used to generate heat. The incineration air entered the fluidized bed from below, with a maximum flow rate of 57 m³•h⁻¹. It was then preheated to 400 °C using a resistance heater, and the flue gas was extracted into the chimney using a smoke fan with a performance of 300 m³•h⁻¹, creating a vacuum. Fuel supply rates were 2.2 – 3.2 kg•h⁻¹, accompanied by primary air flows of 32.0 – 34.6 m³•h⁻¹. Incineration occurred within a temperature range of 875 – 950 °C. The resulting data represents the averages of three 1-h experimental measurements. Throughout operation, the generated fly ash was collected using a cyclone separator, and the flue gas was cooled in two coolers before passing through a filter bag. Thermocouples (accuracy of ± 2.2 °C) and pressure sensors (accuracy of 0.2 %) were positioned at intervals of 200 mm along the top of the device (Jádlovéc and Honus, 2021).

In order to obtain the necessary results, experiments were carried out on the above-mentioned equipment and with the above-mentioned fuel. Three sets of experiments were carried out, each with one and a half hours of incineration tests, averaging the resulting values.

Thus, in these cases, the outlet temperature of the combustor, the quantity and composition of the flue gas were mapped for each fuel, which served as the basis for the energy recovery calculation.

2.6. Life cycle assessment

This study aimed to quantify and compare the environmental impacts of the incineration of PE, SS, and a 50:50 fuel blend. This study built on the results of Jádlovéc et al. (2025) following the general principles and methodologies of the ISO 14040/14044 LCA (Klúppel, 2005). Based on the location of incineration in the Czech Republic, the selected life cycle impact assessment (LCIA) methodology for environmental quantities was the standard ReCiPe 2016v 1.1 (H), with midpoint characterization factors developed by the National Institute for Public Health and the Environment (RIVM) and Radboud University Nijmegen, Netherlands (Huijbregts et al., 2017).

The functional unit (*f. u.*) describing the assessed system is defined as 1 h of incineration, which is required for stable conditions at temperatures of 915 – 939 °C.

This case study focused on the incineration process, which is defined by the principles and methodologies of the gate-to-gate process. All the inventory data for the assessment were obtained through experimental measurements (Table 1), where the LHV values were obtained from fuel analysis.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Angle of repose

The AOR expresses the ability of a material to flow. The lower the angle of repose, the better the flow properties of the material. Based on the angle of repose, the material can be classified into individual flow regimes (Šimek et al., 2017). The angle of repose of the SS was 46°; therefore, its flowability was classified as a cohesive material (poor). The angle of repose for PE was 66° and classified as highly cohesive (very poor), see Table 2.

A value of 66° indicates that the material exhibits flow challenges (e.g., flow of the material into the pelletizing press, dosing, and handling). SS is a cohesive material that does not have such a high tendency to agglomerate and is easier to dose into the pelletizing press than PE. According to the AOR value, PE material is characterized as a highly cohesive material. The PE particles were irregular in shape, cohesive, and more resistant to sliding, and it tended to form larger clumps during processing. Processability and handling during pelletizing can be more problematic. Materials with very poor flowability are difficult to transport through the hopper and can cause arching, i.e., irregular dosing of material into the die during pelletization. This can result in the production of poor-quality pellets and disruption of the pressing process. Therefore, it is preferable to mix it with a material that has a better flowability for further processing.

It is important to mention that the angle of repose, respectively flowability, can be influenced by various factors, such as material moisture, static electricity, morphology, particle size and shape, density and surface (Sandler et al., 2010).

Table 1
Inventory data for individual fuel.

Fuel blend ratio	PE 100 %	PE 1:1 SS	SS 100 %
Fuel quantity [kg]	2.0 ± 0.1	2.8 ± 0.1	3.4 ± 0.1
LHV [MJ•kg ⁻¹]	31.81 ± 0.16	16.29 ± 0.08	9.83 ± 0.05
Ash content [kg]	0.008 ± 0.00016	0.496 ± 0.00992	0.850 ± 0.017
Flue gases [kg]	26.34 ± 1.317	22.557 ± 1.128	21.016 ± 1.051
H ₂ O [kg]	1.149 ± 0.06	1.292 ± 0.07	1.471 ± 0.07
CO ₂ [kg]	1.808 ± 0.05	1.616 ± 0.06	1.861 ± 0.07
CO [mg]	1 213 ± 43	192 ± 11	612 ± 41
NO _x [mg]	1 477 ± 127	13 331 ± 425	13 865 ± 389
NH ₃ [mg]	39.5 ± 8.1	28.3 ± 7.8	33.0 ± 7.2
HCl [mg]	20.8 ± 3.5	153.5 ± 4.6	3 226 ± 74
SO ₂ [mg]	466 ± 68	24 319 ± 1 259	58 840 ± 2 441
CH ₄ [mg]	20.2 ± 1.8	8.0 ± 1.1	96.1 ± 4.9
C ₂ H ₆ [mg]	2.4 ± 0.2	38.2 ± 2.8	111.6 ± 5.7
HF [mg]	7.1 ± 0.4	79.2 ± 4.3	457.7 ± 16.9
O ₂ [kg]	3.310 ± 0.4	2.806 ± 0.3	2.652 ± 0.3
Hg [mg]	95.4 ± 12	385 ± 57	1 787 ± 293
N ₂ [kg]	20.074 ± 1.1	16.804 ± 1.0	14.954 ± 1.1

Table 2
Angle of repose for sewage sludge and polyethylene.

Sample	Angle of repose (°)	Flowability
SS	46	Cohesive
PE	66	Very, very cohesive

3.2. Particle size distribution

Sieve analysis was performed on the SS, and most was captured on a sieve with a mesh size of 3150 μm . The measurement results are shown in Fig. 1.

SS contained a relatively large amount of particles of all measured sizes, all see Figure A.3. SS also contained particles which were $< 1000 \mu\text{m}$ and $> 10000 \mu\text{m}$, because many SS particles remained on both the dish and the 10000 μm mesh sieve. The wide particle size distribution of the SS sample indicated the suitability of the material for pelletization. This led to greater particle connectivity, with smaller particles fitting into the gaps between the larger particles, which increased the strength of the pelletized material (Lisowski et al., 2020). Raw sewage sludge contains a large amount of water and has a very wide particle size distribution (Park et al., 2011).

3.3. Mechanical properties of pellets

The topic of correlations of individual mechanical properties of pellets has been studied for a relatively long time and is conditioned by material properties. In this context, an analysis of the preparation of pellets from energetic grass species was performed (Jezerska et al., 2019). Correlation was applied using principal component analysis (PCA). It was found that a strong positive correlation exists between process temperature, process length, pellet hardness and pellet mechanical resistance.

The WI and hardness were measured for all samples. The WIs of SS, PE, and the blend were 3.54, 12.22, and 3.64 %, respectively. The measurement results are presented in Table 3. The WIs of SS and the blend were almost identical, even though the blend contained 50 % PE, which were not optimum WIs. The WI of the blend was only 0.1 % higher than that of SS. Therefore, the resistance of the pellets to water absorption was mainly influenced by SS. However, it is likely that with a further decrease in SS and an increase in PE in the sample, the WI will increase; thus, the resistance to water absorption will decrease. In most available literature, the use of SS is limited because of its unfavorable water resistance. For example, according to (Chang et al., 2020) the use of SS is limited to 20 %. Another study also mentions that sewage sludge has low resistance to water absorption, because it contains organic matter and has a porous structure (Thukkaram and Kumar, 2024). However, in this study, more SS was present in the pellets, the more resistant they were to water absorption.

SS exhibited the highest hardness and weighed 42 kg. The hardnesses of the blend and PE were 35 kg and 8 kg, respectively, indicating that SS increased the hardness of the pellets. This conclusion is supported by (Jiang et al., 2014), who investigated the effect of SS as an additive on the hardness of biomass pellets. As SS ratio increased, the hardness of the pellets increased, which was predicted from the broad particle size distribution of SS (Fig. 1).

From experimental experience, it can be concluded that pellet hardness has a negative correlation with the wettability index. The exact dependence is not known. Stronger pellets, which are less porous and have a lower specific surface area, absorb less water, and vice versa.

Fig. 1. Particle size distribution for SS.

Table 3
Wettability index and hardness for all samples.

Sample	Wettability index (%)	Hardness (kg)
SS	3.54	42
PE 1:1 SS	3.64	35
PE	12.22	8

3.4. Generation of pollutants from co-incineration

The experiments were conducted in a fluidized bed combustor. Pure PE and SS were incinerated, measured separately, and then blended at a ratio of 1:1. The resulting flue gases were sampled and analyzed. The composition of the flue gases was converted to standard conditions: 101 325 Pa, 273.15 K, dry state, and 11 O₂. The fluidized bed boiler was combusted with an excess of 40 % combustion air, which is supported by (Carsky et al., 2022) who suggested that it should exceed the required amount by 20 – 50 %.

Fig. 4 shows the amount of flue gas generated during the combustion of PE, SS, and the blend. The results show in Fig. 4 an increasing trend for the emitted pollutants, mainly NO_x, where the increase in production was up to 9.7-fold (blend: 9.1-fold), and for SO₂ was up to 130-fold (blend: 53-fold). The highest concentration of nitrogen in the SS was 2.93 %, which is substantially higher than other fuels such as coal (0.5 – 1.5 %) or biomass (0.3 – 1 %) (Liang et al., 2021b). This may result in increased NO_x emissions, typically ranging from 800 to 1 200 mg•m⁻³ (N in the unit stands for “normal” or “standard” conditions) (Sänger et al., 2001); in this study, emissions measured 780 mg•m⁻³. Research from (Wang et al., 2020) evaluated the combustion properties and pollutant emissions of blends of SS and biomass, such as rice husk, peanut husk, and pine sawdust. Their results showed that the SO₂ concentration was up to 5500 mg•m⁻³ when burning pure SS, higher than the 3 310 mg•m⁻³ obtained in this study. At the same time (Wang et al., 2020), the study clearly showed that the SO₂ and NO_x concentrations decrease rapidly with increasing biomass fraction. Another increase was clearly visible for the HF concentration, where the difference between PE and SS was 66.5-fold (blend: 11.3 – fold), and for HCl, where the increase was up to 160-fold (blend: 7.5-fold). CO concentration was 10.63 – 65.97 mg•m⁻³, while the potential for CO reduction lies in the application of over fire air (OFA), which can also further decrease NO_x concentrations (Ma et al., 2020). Therefore, the blend and pure SS exceeded the EU emission limits (Table A.4) (“EUR-Lex - 32019D2010 - EN - EUR-Lex,” 2019) for all measured pollutants. Consequently, flue gas cleaning, such as selective catalytic reduction (SCR) (Zhou et al., 2020) for NO_x or flue gas desulfurization (FGD) (Hanif et al., 2020) for SO₂ reduction, is needed for all measured pollutants. The values that emerged from Fig. 2 were used as input data for the LCA analysis see Table 1.

Similar to the other pollutants, Hg showed a clear upward trend as the SS content of the fuel increased: 5.2, 21.3, and 100.5 µg•m⁻³ for PE, the blend, and SS, respectively. The Hg concentrations of pure SS and the blend were above the EU emission limit of 20 µg•m⁻³ see in Fig. 3. Hg concentration in the flue gas is defined by the curve $y = 7.8928x^2 - 23.523x + 20.816$, $R^2 = 1$. Study by (Lee and Wilcox, 2017) monitored Hg concentrations during the combustion of a coal/SS blend, and their results also showed a dependence of increasing Hg content in the flue gas with increasing SS content. They observed Hg concentrations as high as 35 µg•m⁻³ at a coal-to-SS ratio of 3:1, exceeding those of the blend in this study.

3.5. Energy recovery

To determine the amount of usable energy, energy recovery was defined based on the enthalpy and volume of the flue gas. As shown in Fig. 4, PE had the highest energy recovery at 10.3 MJ•kg⁻¹. The heat recovery parameter decreased with increasing SS content in the fuel, down to 5.3 MJ•kg⁻¹. This decline occurred according to the equation $y = 0.6203x^2 - 4.9713x + 14.677$; $R^2 = 1$.

Fig. 2. The levels of the compounds in the flue gases.

Fig. 3. Mercury concentration in the flue gases.

Similarly, the flue gas volume decreased with increasing SS content, following the equation $y = 0.7529x^2 - 4.9953x + 13.437$; $R^2 = 1$. The results indicated that once the incineration chamber reaches the required temperature, the fuel ignites and burns autonomously without additional preheating, except for preheating the combustion air to a minimum of 300 °C. This is valid for pure PE and fuel blends, except for pure SS (lowest Q_{fg} 5.3 $\text{MJ}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}$), where maintaining a constant incineration temperature without fluidized bed heating is not possible. Therefore, this study proposed using SS for incineration and additional energy recovery more effectively through co-incineration with another fuel. Similarly, (Murakami et al., 2009) found that the application of SS resulted in a significant reduction in the primary fuel, which had a significant impact on energy recovery. Study by (Đurđević et al., 2019) mapped the use of SS in Croatia. The study highlights that sewage sludge incineration in Croatia has significant energy recovery potential, providing an additional 10 – 13 kWh of electricity and 30 – 38 kWh of heat per population equivalent annually. This study developed the two basic methods of energy recovery from SS are anaerobic digestion with biogas incineration and mono-incineration. In Đurđević study the energy recovery through the incineration of SS or biogas from SS would be sufficient to recover 30 – 40 % of electricity consumption and 80 – 100 % of heat consumption at the sewage treatment plant. The LHV of SS was 8.2 – 12 $\text{MJ}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}$, which directly corresponds to our study, as the LHV of our SS was 9.83 $\text{MJ}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}$. Furthermore, as an environmental option, emissions from SS combustion are 58 % lower than those from natural gas combustion and 80 % lower than those from coal combustion.

Fig. 4. Energy recovery and flue gas volume.

3.6. Life cycle assessment

The emissions for one hour of incineration were quantified for the nine main environmental impact categories (climate change, fine particulate matter formation, freshwater ecotoxicity, human toxicity cancer, human toxicity non-cancer, marine ecotoxicity, photochemical ozone formation ecosystems, terrestrial acidification, and terrestrial ecotoxicity) using midpoint characterization factors of ReCiPe 2016v 1.1 (H). The results of the gate-to-gate process and fuel incineration are shown in Fig. 5.

Based on the LHV, the amount of fuel was adjusted to achieve the required temperature and stable incineration conditions. The results showed that CO₂ production correlated with the fuel amount ratio and carbon content in certain fuels; however, the energetic yield of the fuel amount burned to achieve the required conditions was not. This is based on the hydrogen content of clean fuel (PE, SS), which was double the value. Nevertheless, this was not observed in the emissions formation for the concerned impact categories. Study by (Li et al., 2023) evaluates thermochemical conversion technologies of sewage sludge and its impact to climate change (CO₂ eq. production), however the functional unit is adapted to large-scale industrial technologies considering 1 ton of dewatered SS with a moisture content of 80 wt%. Another study by (Jeswani et al., 2021) comparing and evaluating chemical recycling via pyrolysis of mixed plastic waste in comparison with mechanical recycling and energy recovery. In this study was discovered that pyrolysis of mixed plastic waste (MPW) emits 50 % less CO₂ eq. than energy recovery. For better understanding and comparison of this study, the fuel amount and technologies would have to be customized to large-scale together with extension of its boundaries.

The functional unit for the LCA was twice the incineration time compared to a previous study by (Jadlovec et al., 2023). The emissions of individual elements and compounds from the pure blend of SS, which was the same fuel in both analyses, were expected to follow this trend. However, some elements and compounds, such as mercury, hydrogen fluoride, ethane, methane, and hydrochloric acid, are produced exponentially based on the time of incineration.

Most of the impact categories (eight out of nine) showed that it is better to consider and utilize fuel blends more adequately. Particularly, in the climate change impact category, the 50/50 fuel blend was approximately 13 % less harmful than using either of the fuels separately. However, there is one impact category—photochemical ozone formation—that suggested it may be more suitable to use only PE as fuel. Compared to the study by (Jadlovec et al., 2023), where each fuel blend ratio followed a clear development trend in either direction, more variability was observed in this analysis through LCA. Fig. 5 shows the importance of absolute values related to the results.

The limitations of this study include its focus on a single specific blend ratio of sewage sludge (SS) and polyethylene (PE) waste, which may not capture the full potential of other ratios or alternative material combinations. The experimental setup was limited to fluidized bed combustion under controlled laboratory conditions, which may not fully replicate the complexities of large-scale industrial operations. Additionally, the life cycle assessment primarily considered gate-to-gate emissions without evaluating the broader impacts of upstream and downstream processes. Lastly, while the study demonstrates the energy recovery potential and environmental trade-offs, it relies heavily on pollutant mitigation technologies like SCR and FGD, which were not directly analyzed in the context of feasibility or cost-effectiveness. Further investigation is needed to generalize the findings and explore practical applications. The limitation in terms of experimental setup is slightly limited in terms of fluidized bed combustion. If the experiment were repeated in, for example, a grate boiler, slightly different results could be obtained due to different combustion air supply and combustion temperature.

The results of this study indicate strong potential for real-world application of SS and PE blends as alternative fuels. The improved calorific value and mechanical stability of the pellets suggest their suitability for energy generation in fluidized bed combustors, cement kilns, or waste-to-energy plants. These fuels could serve as partial replacements for conventional fossil fuels, offering a sustainable method for waste reduction and energy recovery. From a practical standpoint, the pellets' enhanced hardness and low water absorption improve handling, storage, and transport properties. Their use supports circular economy objectives by diverting waste from landfills and transforming it into a valuable energy source.

Future research should explore performance in larger-scale industrial systems and assess other combustion technologies such as grate-fired boilers, pyrolysis, or gasification. Expanding the scope of the life cycle assessment to include upstream and downstream impacts would provide a more complete environmental profile. Additionally, optimizing the SS-to-PE ratio and testing other plastic or biomass blends could help reduce pollutant emissions. The integration of flue gas cleaning technologies, such as SCR or FGD, also warrants further investigation in terms of cost and efficiency.

Overall, this study lays a foundation for further development of SS-PE-based fuels, supporting waste valorization and low-carbon energy goals.

4. Conclusions

This study highlights the potential of co-incinerating sewage sludge (SS) and polyethylene (PE) waste as an alternative fuel, promoting both waste reduction and energy recovery. Blending SS with PE significantly improved the fuel's lower heating value and mechanical properties, making it more suitable for practical use. However, the process also led to increased emissions of NO_x and SO₂ due to the high nitrogen content in SS. While blending reduces overall emissions compared to SS alone, levels remain higher than those of conventional fuels, warranting environmental consideration. A life cycle assessment confirmed the energy recovery benefits, aligning the approach with circular economy principles. The study emphasizes optimizing fuel composition and incineration conditions to balance energy gain with environmental impact. Its novelty lies in utilizing materials typically destined for landfills. Future research will explore scaling this fuel for larger combustion systems or adapting it for pyrolysis or gasification to enhance sustainability.

Fig. 5. The results of assessed gate-to-gate process in absolute values.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Lucie Jezerská: Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Investigation. **Stanislav Honus:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration. **Marek Jadlovec:** Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Investigation, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Veronika Sassmanová:** Validation, Methodology, Investigation. **Petr Pavlík:** Resources, Formal analysis. **Jan Výtisk:** Writing – original draft, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Veronika Sýkorová:** Investigation, Conceptualization.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendixes

Table A.1

Ultimate and proximate analyses properties of PE, SS, and the blend

Parameter	Symbol	PE	SS (Jadlovec and Honus, 2021)	PE 1:1 SS	Unit	Standard
Carbon	C^r	73.23 ± 0.89	29.07 ± 0.15	42.06 ± 0.28	wt%	ISO 16948
Hydrogen	H^r	8.453 ± 0.01	4.04 ± 0.08	5.34 ± 0.06	wt%	ISO 16948
Oxygen	O^r	16.89*	16.53*	17.06*	wt%	ISO 16993
Sulphur	S^r	< 0.1 ± 0.001	0.69 ± 0.02	0.52 ± 0.02	wt%	ISO 16994
Nitrogen	N^r	0.037 ± 0.001	2.93 ± 0.08	2.08 ± 0.07	wt%	ISO 16948
Water	W^r	0.89 ± 0.01	21.8 ± 0.44	15.65 ± 0.32	wt%	ISO 181234–2
Ash	A^r	0.4 ± 0.001	24.94 ± 0.25	17.72 ± 0.20	wt%	ISO 18122
LHV	LHV^r	31.81 ± 0.49	9.83 ± 0.34	16.29 ± 0.41	MJ•kg ⁻¹	EN 18125

* Calculation value

Fig. A.2. Schematic diagram of the reactor

Fig. A.3. Microscopic photography revealed PE exhibited fibrous structures

Table A.4
Emissions limits for SS as waste in EU ("EUR-Lex - 32019D2010 - EN - EUR-Lex," 2019)

Pollutants	Unit	Emission limit*
NO _x (as NO ₂)	[mg•m ⁻³]	150
SO ₂	[mg•m ⁻³]	40
HCl	[mg•m ⁻³]	8
HF	[mg•m ⁻³]	1
CO	[mg•m ⁻³]	50
NH ₃	[mg•m ⁻³]	10
Hg	[µg•m ⁻³]	20

* Limits under standard conditions and 11 O₂

Table A.5
Impact category results for assessed gate-to-gate process of selected fuels

Impact category	PE	PE 1:1 SS	SS
Climate change, incl. biogenic carbon [kg CO ₂ eq.]	1.8084	1.6167	1.8645
Fine Particulate Matter Formation [kg PM _{2.5} eq.]	0.00030724	0.0085256	0.018597
Freshwater ecotoxicity [kg 1,4 DB eq.]	1.12E-04	4.52E-04	2.10E-03
Human toxicity, cancer [kg 1,4-DB eq.]	6.75E-03	2.73E-02	1.27E-01
Human toxicity, non-cancer [kg 1,4-DB eq.]	2.5689	10.367	48.127
Marine ecotoxicity [kg 1,4-DB eq.]	2.82E-02	0.11371	0.52787
Photochemical Ozone Formation, Ecosystems [kg NO _x eq.]	0.0014773	0.013333	0.01387
Photochemical Ozone Formation, Human Health [kg NO _x eq.]	0.0014772	0.013332	0.013868
Terrestrial Acidification [kg SO ₂ eq.]	0.0010757	0.029173	0.063896
Terrestrial ecotoxicity [kg 1,4-DB eq.]	162	654	3035

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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